

Figure 1: Map showing extent of DOC monitoring at the Balmoral site. Yellow dots indicate the position of the v-notch weirs and photos showing V notch weir.

Protocol for DOC wet chemistry analysis

After samples are delivered to the laboratory the protocol for wet chemistry analysis follows the protocol of the previous National Water Inventory of Scotland (NWIS) project.

Each of the 250ml samples, in plastic bottles, are allocated a James Hutton Institute 'Bible number' a unique ID, traceable throughout the James Hutton Institute.

These samples, as received, have pH and conductivity measurements carried out on them.

Subsequently, approximately 100ml of each sample is filtered through a 0.45µm membrane filter (under vacuum filtration). The remaining unfiltered sample is stored in a cold room and the filter membrane is retained, air dried and stored in plastic bags, for potential further analysis.

The filtered part of the sample is analysed for DOC on a Skalar TOC analyser (Norcross, USA). All results for the wet chemistry analysis of each sample are then recorded in a spreadsheet:

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The filtered sample is then passed on for spectroscopic analysis (see below) and any unused sample is stored in a cold room.

UV-VIS Analysis of DOC samples

After analysis on the Skalar (see above), the filtered DOC samples are analysed on a Shimadzu 1800 UV probe instrument in the range 200nm to 700 nm, following a protocol previously used for the NWIS samples. See Appendix 1 for full details of the method.

As the levels of DOC can be relatively high in the peatland samples, there are occasions where maximum UV-VIS absorbance is reached, and it will be necessary to re-record the spectra using cuvettes with a shorter pathlength.

The spectral data generated by the instrument are saved to an Excel spreadsheet from which the spectra can be plotted as required.

Chemometric Analysis of UV-VIS Spectral Fingerprints of DOC samples

Once a substantial number of spectra have been acquired, models to predict the DOC concentration from the UV-VIS spectra will be developed by correlating the full spectra to measured DOC content. It should also be possible to develop models for prediction of pH and conductivity using the same spectra.

Ultimately the aim would be to develop robust calibrations to predict DOC concentrations in the field using the s::can portable UV-VIS probe (potentially even in real time in the future if cloud processing was possible). As part of the development work for this, UV-VIS spectra of some unfiltered DOC samples (to simulate conditions closer to those in the field) will be recorded for comparison to the filtered samples.

Then UV-VIS spectra of the water samples essentially provide a spectral "fingerprint" which encompasses more than just the DOC (although this is likely to be a major component in the peatland samples) and so it will also be possible to carry out some qualitative work comparing the "fingerprints" from different sites, and different times, within this project. This would give

indications as to the variability of the nature of the dissolved material in the samples, which would be additional to the quantitative information on the concentrations. Wider comparisons to the NWIS dataset, or other peatland sites may also be possible (NWIS reported absorbance at 6 specific wavelengths in the UV-VIS range, but full spectral data should be available).

Fluorescence Analysis of DOC Samples

Fluorescence spectra are also being recorded for the DOC filtered samples on a Gilden Photonics FluoroSENS instrument using 1 cm³ quartz cuvettes and a 150w Xenon lamp as the excitation light source.

Spectra are saved as .csv files prior to being processed in R. The R script used produces information on the nature of the organic matter present in the water e.g., identifying constituents of the sample such as Humics, Fulvics or microbial proteins.

See Appendix 1 for full details of the method.

FTIR of DOC Samples

FTIR spectra will be recorded of freeze-dried down DOC samples, using the DATR sampling accessory on the Bruker Vertex 70 FTIR spectrometer. The samples will require to be freeze dried (filtered portion) to obtain sufficient material (spectra can be recorded of the solutions but would require complex processing of the spectra to remove the water, as it will dominate the spectra). The FTIR will provide a chemical profile of the samples in which the main functional groups present can be identified.

Variation in the chemical profiles can be compared with the UV-VIS spectra to see if we can link the relative proportions of the different components present to the UV-VIS spectra. Spectra will also be compared with spectra of peat samples from above the gullies and spectra of the surfaces of the erosion gullies (see below).

There is also potential for analysing particulates caught on the filters (when the as received samples are filtered for DOC analysis) by FTIR. As it is likely to be difficult or impossible to recover sample material from the filters, the FTIR will need to be directly recorded of the samples on the filter. Depending on the nature of the filters, it may either be possible to identify sufficient bands arising from the sample to characterise it or alternatively to carry out an electronic subtraction of the spectrum of the blank filter from the spectrum of the filter and sample and interpret the subtraction spectrum to determine the nature of the > 0.45µm fraction in the DOC samples.

Raman of DOC samples

There is a possibility that we may be able to carry out Raman analysis on the DOC samples. Raman is not affected by water in the same way as FTIR and could provide additional information on the chemical composition of the organic matter in the DOC samples.

Peat Erosion and Sedimentation Methods

Seven first-order erosion gullies of varying size and length were selected approximately 50-200m south of the UK-BAL eddy covariance tower (56°55'26.1"N 3°09'35.5"W (Fig. 2)). Once one side of each gully nine erosion pins (1m pieces of 8mm threaded rod) were inserted vertically into the peat to the depth of mineral parent soil (Birnie, 1993). Nine erosion pins were inserted in a 1 m² square grid (50 cm spacing) with the top pins 10-20cm from the intact peat and vegetation and the bottom pins close to the gully floor (Fig.3).

Figure 2: Flux tower footprint (Artz et al., 2022) with POC study area to the south.

Sediment traps were installed approximately 3-5m downstream of the erosion pins. These consisted of a water-permeable fabric dug into the ground and reinforced with wire fencing, therefore allowing water through but catching and accumulating peat sediment. Here, three erosion pins were installed 25cm from the fabric, 15cm apart (Fig. 3). The length of exposed erosion pin was measured at t₀ (27/09/2022) with anticipated repeat measurements approximately every 3-4 months (gully side pins expected to increase in exposed length, sediment trap pins expected to decrease).

We will extend peat erosion and sedimentation studies to Glensaugh in 2023.

Figure 3: Photograph of a gully with erosion pins (foreground) and sediment trap (background)

Soil sampling for FTIR spectra

At each erosion gully, we will take 3 soil cores using a box corer from the intact peat above the erosion feature (one core per gully has already been taken). We will then decide at which depths to take samples at. On the gully edge we will take peat samples adjacent to each erosion pin from the top 1cm and at 5cm. This would mean 18 sediment samples per gully (9 pins * 2 depths) + how many depths per intact soil core we take. We will also collect soils at the sediment traps for FTIR analysis once a significant amount has accumulated.

The cores would be subdivided into the relevant depths and then air dried and ball milled prior to FTIR analysis using the DATR sampling accessory.

The aims here are to 1. Test the variability of SOM composition by depth and spatial variance, 2. Test whether peat SOM 'fingerprints' become homogenised as they enter the erosion process and 3. Test whether SOM becomes significantly oxidised in this initial erosion stage.

Peat motion cameras

At the Balmoral Site, we will use repeated LiDAR surveys of peat topography using a UAV to understand large scale peat movement and link with fine scale measurements of peat erosion. We will also trial peat motion cameras, a low cost but highly accurate approach to measuring vertical peat motion, particularly subsidence (Evans et al. 2021 <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2021.630752>). These will provide an accurate time series of peat motion and an independent verification of larger scale lidar measurements from the UAV platform.

Appendix 1 - Methods used in UV-Vis and Fluorescence of Balmoral samples

Full instruction on using the Shimadzu 1800 UV probe instrument can be found on the intranet <http://connect.hutton.ac.uk/Organisation/HSQE/SEP/Forms/WKs.aspx#InplviewHashbacbf034-c569-4896-bd3c-ed3c1633027=>

WK-165 Shimadzu UV probe

Synopsis of method to produce data from UV

After switching on and allowing the instrument to warm up and complete its switch on checks, set the required wavelengths (200nm – 700nm), milliQ water is placed into the 2 Cuvettes and a Baseline is completed.

Using the front cuvette, rinse it twice with a small volume of the sample before filling with the sample. Run the scan, save the scan into the correct directory and identify the file with the sample barcode. Rinse the cuvette with several washes of MilliQ water before filling with the next sample following the prerinse before filling with the sample.

Leave all the sample scans open and press “Data icon” from the menu tab. Select “edit” and “Select All”, select Copy and copy all.

In excel select “paste”, the data should now fill the columns with column A containing the wavelength, from column B onwards this contains the absorbance values for the samples, in a blank row at the top of the sheet start in column B and insert the sample barcode and continue moving along the column’s adding the barcodes until all the samples have a barcode ID.

In the UV software click onto anywhere on the data and this should deselect the data, highlight one of the columns this will show you which scan matches the data, check the excel values against the UV data, do this for several more to check that the sample barcode on the excel sheet matches the file barcode ID.

Synopsis of Spectrofluorescence method to produce data from FluoroSENS

Operating manuals for the Spectrofluorometer and the contour visual software (scan processing data) are available to download from the lab PC.

A Gilson Photonics FluoroSENS instrument is used to run samples for Fluorescence using Quartz cuvettes 1cm³ and 150w Xenon lamp as the excitation light source.

The instrument is switched on first, then the software icon is opened on the PC and the instrument should connect automatically (there are 3 parameters which will display “succeed” before the software opens for use), the instrument is allowed to warm up for approximately 30 minutes.

The cuvette is filled with MilliQ water, inserted into the holder, from the software select – file – new-EM icon - choose “Raman_1S.fcp” then start the software – this is done daily as a method of checking the lamp intensity (it does drop off over time as the lamp ages). Hover the mouse pointer over the peak maximum and note this down, save as “Raman date”

Usually, weekly a scan is taken of the MilliQ water as this gets used when processing the data in “R”.

From the software select – file – new – EEM (ladybird icon) Samia_1_short.fcp. Select start and this will scan the sample, once complete use file save as (Barcode ID), next click export from the icon menu, select – data and save as a XML format (Barcode ID).

Rinse the cuvette twice with a small volume of the sample before filling with the sample. Run the scan, save the scan into the correct directory, and identify the file with the sample barcode. Rinse the cuvette with several washes of MilliQ water before filling with the next sample following the prerinse before filling with the sample.

When processing the scan files ready to be used in R the Contour Visualiser software is used. Open the software

Click the Import... button to load your scan data. Note the scan data should be in XML format. The data is loaded and displayed in a chart which takes up most of the window. Select “contour” and change the threshold to 10000 to start with, this can be reduced until you are happy with the scan, and you can see the contours revealed. Click Save – JPG and TXT format (Barcode ID as file name).

In excel open the TXT file, save as a csv file format. In this format it is ready for final processing in “R”.

Script from R is available to process the data and print out a graph indicating the constituents of the sample such as Humics, Fulvics or microbial proteins.